

IMPLEMENTATION OF ECOPRENEUR CONCEPT IN CREATING GREEN FASHION

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Abstract

Based on survey data of the Creative Economy Agency (Bekraf) and Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) in 2016 showed that the Creative Economy sector contributed 7.38 percent of the total national economy. Current fashion trends are no longer based on two or four seasons, but rather lead to a fast cycle of 6 - 8 weeks then switch to a new one, this is commonly known as fast fashion. Fast fashion focuses on speed and low production costs to produce the latest collection. Pressures to reduce costs and time in producing fashion products impact negative environmental impacts caused by water pollution, the use of toxic chemicals and increased levels of textile waste. To overcome these problems then the awareness needed in maintaining the environment of the fashion industry players. This study aims to determine the extent to which the implementation of ecopreneur concept in fashion industry players. The method used is a qualitative method by describing and portraying the empirical reality behind the phenomenon in depth, detailed and complete. This research was conducted by observation and semi-structural interview on the ecopreneur fashion distro in Bandung city.

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1. Introduction

Paul Hawken (1993) in his book which entitled the ecology of commerce: a declaration of sustainability, stated that every business has three basic issues to face according to environmental problems. Firstly, business uses too much natural resources for their production. Secondly, production requires excessive amounts of energy. Lastly, the method of manufacture is not environmentally friendly that can harm to present and future generations. These arguments indicate that every business activity needs to concern for environmental problems and entrepreneurs need to carry a responsibility to address these environmental problems. Environmental issues began to be discussed since the United Nations held a conference of the environment in Stockholm, Sweden, on June 15, 1972. The Indonesian Environmentalists Association (HPLI) revealed that environmental problems were related to high rapidly population growth rates. This rapid rate

growth generates development and industrialization. As a result, industrialization can accelerate the supply of human life needs but on the contrary, it provides a negative impact to environment.

Fashion became a part of the main human needs. So that, the fashion industry is becomes a promising business commodity and continues to expand. Current fashion trends are longer based on two or four seasons, but rather than leading to a fast cycle of 6 - 8 weeks, then switch to a new one, this is commonly known as fast fashion. Fast fashion focuses on speed and low production costs to produce the latest collection. Pressures to reduce costs and time in producing fashion products create negative impact to the environment caused by water pollution, the use of toxic chemicals and increased levels of textile waste. As a result, the fashion industry is become the second largest pollutant following oil in the world.

For example, cotton, which is the most commonly used material for clothing, is a contributor to soil and water damage caused by using pesticides. Because of cotton growth requires high levels of water and pesticides to prevent crop failure. The use of synthetic materials is also not the best solution for substitutes cotton. Artificial fiber materials such as polyester, nylon, spandex and acrylic are the most popular materials used in fashion industry. However, when its washed they release 1.900 microfiber that escalate level of plastic in the water which contaminate the aquatic ecosystem.

Textile waste is an unwanted result of fast fashion. More people buy clothes and do not store them for a long time. Massive fast fashion retail expansion aggravates problems on a global scale. Fashion retailers tempt and persuade buyers with new collections. As a result, people are more fascinated in buying cheap and new goods than recycling used goods.

Environmentally fashion business or commonly referred to green fashion is one of the many solutions to solve environmental problems. This type of business can create recycled fashion products that reduce the waste problem. Sometimes entrepreneurs not concern about the impact their business activities to the environment. For example, when products in the hands of consumers, packages and wastes because of product consumption are no longer part of the company's consideration.

Nevertheless, green fashion besides being able to increase entrepreneurs' income also provide hope for a bright future for sustainable development. in Indonesia, this business is not only important for the environment but also a solution for poverty alleviation. Therefore, this research aims to explore ecopreneur in creating green fashion business. This study focused on four fashion distribution stores (distro) in Bandung City, the capital province of West Java, Indonesia.

2. Indonesian Creative Economy Outlook

Indonesia's economic growth in 2018 is forecast to increasing as result of the reinforcement of investment. Higher prices of global commodity boosted investment improvement. This has resulted fastest capital grew in the last 5 years. However, investment enhancement led to elevate the rate of import, which grew over than twice the velocity of exports, which potentially obstruct on economic growth. Even so, Indonesia's economic growth outlook are predicted to have a positive trend. Based on reports of the World Bank, global economic growth is projected to slow, and trade flows moderate from recent highs. Indonesia's GDP growth is predicted to still increase with domestic demand robust from 5.1 percent in 2017 to 5.2 percent in 2018 [2].

Creative economy sector is different from other industries. The vigor of creative economy not depend on the exploitation of natural resources but highly on the excellences of human resources in creating ideas and creative thinking. Based on the Republic of Indonesia Presidential Regulation Number 6 of 2015 concerning the Creative Economy Agency, on January 20, 2015, the Indonesian government formed a new non-ministerial institution called the Creative Economy Agency (Bekraf). This agency is responsible on creative economy development in Indonesia.

Indonesia's economy accrued by 5.02% in 2016, the third highest after India and China among the G20 countries and one of the best in the world, with creative economy has an important contribution in advancing the Indonesian economy. Based on survey data of the Bekraf and Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) in 2016 showed that the creative economy sectors were contributed 7.38 percent or 852 trillion rupiahs of the total national economy and able to permeated 15,9 million labors in 2015 [3]. Aside as a driving force for the national economy, the creative economy industry is one of methods to preserve Indonesian cultures. It has a role in creating value added of image and identity of the nation. This can impact the society to love and proud using local products. Therefore, the government needs to provide full consideration for creative economy industry advancement.

The creative economy is a new era of economics after agricultural economics, industrial economy, and information economy, which intensify information and creativity by relying on ideas and knowledge from human resources as the main production factors in economic activities. The creative economy was grouped into 16 sub-sectors: (1) architecture; (2) interior design; (3) visual communication design; (4) product design; (5) films, animations and videos; (6)

photography; (7) handicraft; (8) culinary; (9) music; (10) fashion, (11) software and game developers; (12) publishing; (13) advertising; (14) television and radio; (15) performing arts; and (16) fine arts (4).

3. Fashion Sub-Sector Business

In Indonesia, fashion sub-sector was contributed 154,694 billion rupiahs or equal to 18.15% of the total creative economy PDB in 2015 with 2.80 percent PDB growth rate. Beside contribute to economic grow, the fashion sub-sector was becoming the largest contributor to exports of creative economy products value by 56 percent with West Java as the largest contributor of fashion products export by 42.52 percent. In addition, 24 percent of the total workforce in the national creative economy worked in the fashion subsector (3). Moreover, fashion sub-sector become the second largest developer of Indonesian creative economic following culinary sub-sector. This shows that the awareness of Indonesian people to fashion sub-sector is elevating.

The creative economy industry in West Java province, Indonesia is growing swiftly, particularly at Bandung City, which is dubbed as Emerging Creative City. This image has been promoted Bandung City as an attraction and economic mover in West Java. According to the West Java Regional Government Implementation Report (2016), Bandung is the only area in West Java Province that has forming creative industries as their main activity. It has been a long time ago Bandung become a destination for people who searching for culinary tourism and fashion products.

The development of the fashion industry in Bandung has been well thrived. Bandung was knowing as the center of fashion in Indonesia and they were called Paris Van Java. Local brands emerged as a form rapid growth of factory outlets (FO) and distribution stores (Distro) as distribution agents for creative textile products.

4. Ecopreneurship

The concept of ecopreneurship began to be discussed in early of 1990. Several studies conducted by Bennett (1991), Berle (1991) and Blue (1990) use the term 'environmental entrepreneur', 'green entrepreneur', 'eco-entrepreneur' which is the origin of the term ecopreneurship, as a term for entrepreneur-based environment (5). According to Kirkwood and Walton (2008) ecopreneurs are defined as those entrepreneurs who found new businesses based on the principle of sustainability. In other hand, ecopreneurs are entrepreneurs who enter these eco-friendly markets not only to make profits, but also having strong, underlying green values.

From his statement we can conclude that ecopreneur is an entrepreneur those who enter an environmentally friendly market are not just looking profit, but also has strong environmental values as the foundation.

Schaper (2002) explains that the adoption of business practices those responsible for the environment can open new opportunities for an entrepreneur. This includes the development of the product or new service, company improvement for efficiency, new methods for marketing activities and reconfiguration of business models and practices. The importance of ecopreneurship is not only due to being able to creates new opportunities, but also have the potential to be the main drivers in transition of sustainable business paradigm. Ecopreneurship is a potential alternative for facing environmental negative influence of market failure (8). Under this condition, ecopreneur acts as a pulling factor that invites entities of businesses to proactively more concern about the environment. Ecopreneurship as the intersection of the entrepreneurship and the sustainability discipline having framed by 3 sub-concepts: eco-innovation, eco-commitment, and eco-opportunity.

4.1 Eco-innovation,

According to Rennings in Kainrath (2009), eco-innovation focused on innovation to reduce environmental problems. It was also emphasized that unsustainable development as the result of rapid technological changes. Therefore, social innovations such as changes in lifestyle need to be done to overcome environmental problems. According to Halila and Horte in Kainrath (2009), eco-innovation consists of six categories: (1) Product care (category 1), Sustainability of existing products and no influence the real change in the environment is better. (2). Minor product improvement (category 2), improvement of several aspects or components of the product that changes to environmentally friendly product components. (3) Major product improvement (category 3), Produce new products or fundamental changes in existing product. Make products or services where the components are more than 50% environmentally friendly. (4) Functional Innovation (category 4), innovation in creating new functions of a product as the principle of a new solution. (5) System innovation (category 5), the result in changes of existing systems and creative contributions that can change scientific fields. This can be change in products, production chain, infrastructure and consumer behavior. (6) Breakthrough Scientific (Category 6), eco-friendly discoveries that have broad scale influence or able to influence several industries.

4.2 Eco-commitment

In Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary states that commitment to something is willingness to work hard and give you energy and time to a job or activity. From this statement we can conclude

that commitment is the desire to work hard and dedicate energy and time for a job or activity. Keogh and Polonsky (1998) explained that commitment would encourage the vision of an ecopreneur to be considered about what is important, what is useless, what is needed and what is not needed.

There are three categories in Eco-commitment (9). Firstly, affective commitment is emotional attachment to the consideration in environmental issues and achieving environmental goals. This commitment is a strongest commitment that will trigger ecopreneur to prioritize environmentally friendly solutions rather than non-environmentally solution. This commitment is not only able to guide to radical eco-innovation but also will lead to utilization of eco-opportunities. Secondly, the commitment which is focusing on economic and social costs called continual commitment. The costs that an ecopreneur spend when overriding environmental problems, known as opportunity costs. This commitment is focused on costs, both tangible neither intangible is invested as concern for environment. Lastly, a commitment of ecopreneur which driven by a feeling of obligation or feeling of debt mind is called normative commitment. This commitment basically sticking to the norm or environmental protection law. Normative commitment will form eco-opportunity and eco-innovation because of all parties feel obliged to protect the environment.

4.3 Eco-opportunity.

Dean and McMullen in Kainrath (2009) explained that market failure is happen when economic activity causes environmental degradation or social damage. This market failure means failure of most or a small part of the ideal system on market price. Based on the concept of entrepreneurship this market failure become an opportunity when business can create products or services more environmentally friendly. The use of opportunities for environmental degradation is called eco-opportunity. By utilizing eco-opportunity, ecopreneur has reduce environmental damage.

Eco-opportunity consists five categories Kainrath (2009). First, products that owned by public without except and can consume indefinitely are general goods (public goods). Ecopreneur needs to manage environmental resources for the public interest but also develop and strengthen property rights that mitigate environmental damage. Second, loss or profits that come about in a transaction is called externalities. It can't describe by price but influencing transaction with third parties. In this condition, when ecopreneur is attempting to reduce transaction cost, they ensure that environmentally relevant are positive and negative externalities are produced in amounts acceptable to society and environment. Third, when monopoly behaviors take aim for maximizing profit, it will instigate market failures. Furthermore, because of lack of competition, monopoly

frequently run inefficiently and turn out more wastes. Ecopreneur, who mitigate environmental impact, acts as a controller of environmental management for the existence monopoly power.

Fourth, inappropriate government intervention misleads incentives and expenses for economic players which results in environmental deprivation if the government supports industries that are damaging to the environment. Ecopreneurs can influence the government intervention to protect the environment from damage. Last, imperfect information may lead to market failure, and if the imperfect information indicates to increase environmental effect, the market failure appropriate to inadequate information causes environment deprivation. An ecopreneur be able to overrun this eco-opportunity by enlightening consumers about the environmental features of a product. The knowledgeable consumer's buy decision of environmentally friendly products reduces environmental damage because of the exchange of environmentally harmful products with more environmentally friendly ones.

5. Research Purpose

The main purpose of this research is to give an exploration of ecopreneurship concept from green fashion business activities. Although, information from this research will be valuable inputs for the actual research which will be conducted in the very near future.

6. Research Method

This study involved local clothing distribution store which implement green-fashion concepts. This research using a qualitative model where it involved interpretive and descriptive analysis of words from conversation with the respondents. Four local clothing brands are selected and interviewed. Information were collected use semi-structure interview of research protocol. The interview medium were Indonesian languages to ensure accuracy and inclusive information collected from the respondents.

7. Findings

Respondents in this study were four well-known local distribution store owners in the city of Bandung. To ensure anonymity, the researcher named the first distribution store as F, the second distribution store as A, the third distribution store as S, and the last distribution store as O (not their real name). all four-run green fashion business activities as part of their distribution store's main business activities. Discussion of the categorization of ecopreneurship activities carried out by distribution store with a theoretical approach to aspects of ecopreneurship introduced by

Kainrath (2009). In his explanation, Kainrath revealed that there are three aspects to ecopreneurship, namely first eco-innovation, second eco-commitment and finally eco-opportunity. In this qualitative research, we gained three insights into various research questions to green fashion business activities in Bandung.

Firstly, the discussion on eco-innovation refers to the concept described by Halila and Horte where eco-innovation is measured by developing ideas, behaviors, products and processes, implementing activities or introducing which contribute to the reduction of the burden on the environment carried out by related parties (5). There are 6 categories of innovations in eco-innovation, they are product care, minor product improvement, major product improvement, functional innovation, system innovation, and scientific breakthrough. Based on six categories of eco-innovation described by Halila and Horte, F and S distribution stores innovation conducted minor product improvement. They develop on several aspects or components of existing products, such as reduce the use of plastic as their campaign about environmental concern, to aims consumers more caring to the environment. In addition, distributions store A innovation carried out major product improvement. The ecopreneur of distribution store A innovates existing product to become a new product. This is based on the statement of the A distro owner who stated that he had produced t-shirts made from bamboo fiber which is decrease the fashion wastes, to provide a message to consumers about eco-friendly fashion products. Meanwhile, O distributions store had taking eco-innovation of category five, namely the innovation system, that innovates existing systems for creating new environmentally friendly systems. For example, in producing a jacket, distribution store O used a 45-degree pattern technique for more effectively use of raw materials and reduce the production scrap.

Secondly, the second aspect of ecopreneurship is eco-commitment. The discussion of eco-commitment aspects is carried out based on Keogh and Polonsky's theory which explains that there are 3 types of eco-commitment, namely affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment (5). Based on three categories of eco-commitment by Keogh and Polonsky identified that O, A and S distributions stores eco-commitment categorized into normative commitment. Normative commitment is a commitment in the form of a response to feelings of obligation or debt due to external influences or individual obligations to the environment. They commitment emerged to be more environmentally friendly was influenced more by external factors. Currently, they are doing environmentally friendly activities only in the form of a gimmick. They are waiting for the government policy to obligate requiring of environmentally friendly products. The absence of a government policy regarding green fashion products causes

half-hearted on O, A and S distributions stores to carry out the concept of environmentally products.

Meanwhile, the F distribution stores eco-commitment identified in the category affective commitment. Affective commitment is a commitment to the environment in the form of emotional attachment to the environment. The F distribution store carried out their business activities not only in addition to obtaining income but also give benefits to surroundings. The commitment is reflected in their business process concept that have added value of money but also still carries the concept of environmental concern, such as reducing the use of plastic bags, social campaigns, discount programs through book donations.

The last aspect of ecopreneurship is eco-opportunity. The discussion of aspects of eco-opportunity refers to the theory of Dean and McMullen which explains that market failures are related to the environment. However, if the community is given a more cost-effective solution, they will pay the fee to eliminate market failure. There are 5 types of eco-opportunity, namely public goods, externalities, monopoly power, inappropriate government intervention, and imperfect information (5).

In ecopreneurship activities run by F, A, S and O distribution stores, the eco-opportunity is utilized is the opportunity into imperfect information. Imperfect information is a situation where there is information related to the environment that is not known by others. There are two types of imperfect information. Firstly, ignorance of producers regarding the supply of environmentally friendly technologies. Lastly, ignorance of consumer preferences for green products. The opportunity of imperfect information utilized by these distributions stores is information about consumer preferences related to green products. For consumers, the costs problem incurred in buying environmentally friendly products is not become the main problem. They preferred accordance the quality of the product as they expect or exceed their expectations. In addition, the campaign to reduce the use of plastic bags encourages consumers to reduce the use of plastic bags themselves. This marketing system has attracted the attention of new consumers who have concern for the environment.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, all the well-known local distribution store in the city of Bandung have implemented 3 aspects of ecopreneurship, namely eco-innovation, eco-commitment, and eco-opportunity. In the eco-innovation aspect, F and S distribution stores make small product improvements by developing several components from existing product. A

distribution store innovates products to become new products. O distribution store innovates the existing system to create a new environmentally friendly system.

In the aspect of eco-commitment O, A, and S stores uses normative commitment which is a response to obligations that arise due to external factors or individual obligations to the environment. F store uses affective commitment that not only prioritizes income but also its benefits to the environment. The last in the eco-opportunity aspect all stores use imperfect information opportunities where there are situations with information related to the environment that is not known to others.

The implementation of ecopreneurship in the fashion industry in this case is the distro entrepreneurs in the city of Bandung, currently not yet in the form of a comprehensive concept. The ecopreneurship program is only in the form of sweeteners in the distribution business because the distribution business people themselves do not understand the concept of green fashion itself. In addition, the government has not been able to facilitate fashion businesses in the city of Bandung to develop eco-friendly fashion products. This can be seen from the absence of government policies regarding eco-friendly fashion products in the form of coaching, training, infrastructure facilities, and recognition of environmentally friendly products.

Other support also needs to be given by employers, banks and the academic community in providing investment funding, developing eco-fashion business and developing sustainable eco-fashion concepts. So that it is expected to produce, namely: 1. Entrepreneurs - new entrepreneurs who have high knowledge about eco fashion products, 2. The concept of developing eco fashion products that are in line with consumer needs 3. Increasing public awareness of environmentally friendly products

Environmental issues that have been developing in Indonesia have been largely an issue of waste. Therefore, the fashion business in the field of green business in Indonesia is always associated with the processing of waste to become a fashion product that has added value or also called a recyle. But the business of eco-friendly fashion products currently has a very limited market. Business in the field of eco-friendly fashion is still doubtful the ability to be accepted by the community. Some things that become obstacles for environmentally friendly fashion products are: 1. The price of raw materials is quite high. 2. Lack of ability to meet market demand. 3. The existence of unstable raw materials. 4. Quantity of production volume that tends to be low. 5. An undeveloped market.

There is hope that in the future this product will be in demand as consumers care about eco-friendly fashion products that are increasingly increasing in addition to the strength of unique recycle products. Business development in this field basically must be carried out by those who are very familiar with the environmentally friendly fashion industry and business management of these products to be able to achieve the goals effectively and efficiently.

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